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Sustainability And The Aesthetics Of Birds' Plumage: Rethinking Non-Human Actors In Art

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ABSTRACT

This study examines contemporary artworks that showcase natural aesthetics to exhibit their artistic expressions in order to ascertain the rightful place of the non-human actors in the insights shared by their expressions. Scholarly opinions emphasize unfavourable divides on related grounds about the subject of non-human animal forms in artistic forums. While some hold the view that despite their aesthetic appeal and the potentials they bring into the frame, they are actors in their own right. Contrarily, others establish that despite the valuable insights expressed by non-human animals in artistic works, they are not actors in their own right. This study views the introduction of non-human animals through the structures of birds' plumages in contemporary artistic expressions, highlighting their aesthetic potentials as actors, from the lens of ornithological perspective. It suggests that art works loss their aesthetic qualities, insights, potentials, and technical representation, where the non-human animals are exempted from the artistic frame. The results of this study has implication for the philosophical content of contemporary artistic expressions, also, it shared valuable insights that are essential for professional artists, academics, environmental art, and activism.

Keywords: Aesthetics, Art Ontology, Art Ornithology, Avian Plumages

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, contemporary art aesthetics expresses non-human animals in nature, ascribed by culture. Non-human animals are broadly accepted as artless beings without the desired capacity to create aesthetic objects. Contrarily, the need for creative art anticipates a threshold that is fixed on humanity. Contemporarily, artists establish aesthetic artworks with living non-human animals in studio painting (Seddon, 2020). These visual appeals declare most non-human animals as co-authors of artworks with a reasonable degree of trust in their potential as creative agents (Straffon, 2021). Consequently, such artworks express the legitimacy of animal potentials as contributors to sculptures, paintings, installations, video works, and other artistic displays.

The state of the nature of living non-human animals, their ecological systems in intricate dimensions, indicates aesthetic appeals to humanity in art, philosophy, anthropology, sciences, and other fields of endeavor (Ullrich, 2024). These perspectives give art the opportunity to delve into the aesthetics of non-human animals by using diverse interdisciplinary methods and viewpoints across history (Johnson & Leon, 2023). These living non-human animals are natural potential actors that express the health and wealth of our co-community relationships in artworks.

Relatively, nature in this art expression of living non-human animals is the comprehensive structure on which the concept and material of these actors undergo the circles of the decay and rebirth of the beauty expressed by these living and non-human forms in studio paintings (Widow, 2018). This highlights a rooted human kinship ascribed by nature with a perception that reshapes aesthetics expressed by these forms, which are altered over time.

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Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to view the introduction of non-human animals in artistic expression and highlight their aesthetic potentials as actors in their own right. It focuses on studio painting works that bring into existence the structural forms of avian plumage to express the aesthetic of non-human animal form in the arts. It clarifies this simile-unrelated truth that the participation of non-human animals systematically represents forms of agency, but these non-human forms cannot be showcased as artists in the limelight of studio painting expression (Ankar & Flach, 2024; Widow, 2018).

Research Question

The research question states that in abstract art expressions do non-human animals' aesthetics convey their potentials as actors in their own right?

Significance of the Study

The study is beneficial to artist, especially those in the studio, who rely on using references whenever they engage in studio exploration that involves adaptation/appropriation of an images/images into their artwork to enhance a comprehensive conclusion. Also, the study is significant because it draws the attention of studio artists who strive for originality to the natural aesthetics of the birds

2. Literature Review

Ornithological perspective of birds

In the seventeenth century, interest in birds centred largely on folklore and their symbolic significance. The ornithology perspective marked a turning point in the study of birds by rejecting folklore and focusing especially on biology. Following Ray's *Wisdom of God* (1691), which addressed the ultimate causes, the study of birds is developed along two separate strands: (i) systematics, nomenclature, and faunistic (inspired by Ornithology) and (ii) natural history (inspired by *Wisdom*) (Internet Archive, 2024). The first of these endeavours dominated ornithology for the next 250 years and was the main focus of the ornithological Unions founded in the 1800s. The two strands were reunited in the 1920s (central Europe) and 1940s (the UK and the USA) (Birkhead & Charmantier, 2009). After World War II, not only did the expansion of higher education result in a huge increase in both the number of professional ornithologists, but also our knowledge of avian natural history and evolution (Delfino, 2024).

Ornithology and bird aesthetics

Throughout history, humans have had a deep and complex connection with birds, plants, and other species of animals (Ullrich, 2024; Birkhead & Charmantier, 2009). The study of how humans and birds interact has the potential to provide valuable insights for the advancement of bird ecology and conservation (Katz, 2015). This review illustrates how this area has developed over time, with main sub-topics and the expression of the direction it should take in the future within ethno-ornithology (Birkhead & Charmantier, 2009). Four major themes stand out:

- (i.) The study of birds with archaeological findings through ancient societies'
- (ii.) The examination of traditional and indigenous knowledge about bird ecology;
- (iii.) The exploration of the symbolic roles birds play in the arts and media;
- (iv.) The investigation of the various ways humans and birds interact.

By acknowledging the cultural and historical importance of birds, modern ornithologists can bridge the gap between scientific research and public engagement, helping to raise awareness and foster efforts aimed at bird conservation through contemporary art (Newman, 2019; Birkhead & Charmantier, 2009). This practice celebrates art through the observations depicted by other artists as they express this aesthetics that appears to be tongue in cheek, but most of such expression connote significant truth (Widow, 2018). The works of these artists express the feeling that theory is not relevant to explain what they do, as there is no way to explain it or describe it in any theoretical way, in the process of artistic creation (Newman, 2019). In this light, this expression reveals that speaking about art prevents the art from speaking for itself. Certainly, it seems true that many artists are suspicious about or reluctant to talk about their work.

The artistic representation of non-living humans in artworks has a unique appeal besides their cultural relevance, religious symbolism, metaphorical provocations, and extraordinary knowledge, beyond passive aesthetic objects in art representations (Ullrich, 2024). Theoretically, non-living human aesthetic expressions in art highlight passionate appeal independent of the facts and insights, the perception of the artist upholds (Ullrich, 2024).

Essentially, these contemporary arts unknowingly focus on non-living humans, to technically share and highlight factual information, to hint at the aesthetic satisfaction in the beauty of the artwork (Johnson & Leon, 2023). Philosophically, these non-living humans' aesthetics generate the ideas from the dimensions of the slickness of their plumages, plus the perspectives from which the beauties expressed in their colours are reinterpreted and manifested in contemporary art (Ullrich, 2024). This transformation involves understanding how peacock's vibrant iridescent colours and intricate feathers structure inspire artistic design and sustainability practices (as shown in figure 2a). The perceived aesthetics of peacock feathers and their structural beauty with even symmetrical structures and transverse arrangement of bright colours, are indicated as recurring motives in conventional arts (as shown in Figure 2b). These act arrangements present aesthetics as a humanistic discipline, which is determined by the portrayal of non-human animals as beings with no capacity for aesthetic sensibility, a form of human exceptionalism assumption linked to the production of knowledge about non-human animals to express aesthetics (Johnson & Leon, 2023; Mieza, 2015).

Knowingly, the bright presentation of its blue, Yellow, Dark green, leaf green, Orange and Crimson Red Colours have social aesthetic Representations that express its adaptation features. The Royal blue and the yellow species give adaptive impressions that expresses distinct universal appeal of stability, unity, and conservative intelligence (see figure 3a). This shows that birds are beings with complex, surprising aesthetic sensibilities, beyond the adaptationist idea that the perception of beauty is influenced in non-human animals as favoured by nature for ecological survival (Johnson & Leon, 2023). Also deeply expressed colour reflections mediate the appearance of translucent calmness that conforms with the intensive innate calmness of these colours expressed in plumages of these birds (Smith, 2021).

Understanding how the Brazilian Royal blue-yellow Parrot's vibrant iridescent colours, intricate feature and structure inspire artistic design for sustainability art practices (as shown in figure 4). Insight into the sustainability of blue-and-yellow parrots raises a lot of interest in their uniqueness. Basically, it is a rainforest creature that provokes a sense of admiration from conservationist animal activists on the protection of its biodiversity (Borgmann, 2023). In art, its majestic colour and appearance connote natural beauty, neatly connected to its ecosystem and forest life.

Figure 1a & 1b: Shutterstock (2025). Blue yellow parrot royal. Top image by Ciobanivc Adrian Eugen, shutterstock.com, 30th June.

In studio painting, most artist emphasises the use of its intricate lace colours in design, some tap into the uniqueness of its size and discrete plumages to express the effect of its appearance as a distinct design to illustrate other artistic forms (Okoye, 2024; Mieza, 2015). Generally, in art and studio painting in particular, a stunning peacock craft ensures serenity with a stronghold of self-possession. Relatively, it is a symbol of tranquillity that inspires emotional balance, which supports freedom from stress. To proclaim its sustainability beyond its conservation status, artworks, crafts, sculptures, in parks and gardens to display its natural grandeur in city centres.

Figure 2a & 2b: Pavo-cristatus. African peacock. Free image Lesik A. shutterstock.com. top image by Lesik. A 21 May 2018.

This cautious expression awakens our consciousness to purposefully guide this natural beauty as a sustainable luxury where conservation efforts are extended to its ecological sustainability (Borgmann, 2023). Further, efforts to sustain the ecological system in abstract arts represent the full Splendour of peacock gracefulness in different textures and forms indirect relation to its elegance in connection to nature (Mieza, 2015). A perfect translation by choice to extend its plumage as a striking symbol of ecological friendliness (Nkwocha, 2024; Borgmann, 2023).

Sustainability and Adaptation

Brazilian Royal blue-yellow Parrot and the Peacock: The Hypothesis designated to Zahavian signal basically depends on the indirect benefits of the male species, where its genetics is a direct reliable indicator of its quality of life, which is directly transferred across generations. The adaptive aesthetics of the peacock is in full display as it showcases a broad spectrum of its tail (see figure 1b). This expression reveals the general physical condition of this non-human form. It indicates its strong health to its accomplice with risk for the maintenance of such a beautiful display, with consequences for its high-quality male status (as seen in Figure 2b). The display has been attributed to as a waste of energy and a costly social signal (Miller, 2016; Jones & Ratterman, 2009). This is a clear expression in ornamental art that reorients the Zahavian hypothesis (Straffron, 2021; Seddon, 2020). This is because the bright plumages of the peacock in full expression of the peacock is a beneficial selection strategy driven by perceptual preferences with sensory bias on social information that is not only valuable for these non-human forms, but is intrinsically essential for aesthetics in conventional studio painting (Anderson & Simmons, 2006).

This artistic expression of broad tail feathers of these non-human forms is an expression of dynamic beauty and purposeful vibration of elegant pictorial symbols in glossy display that are ascribed to the Zahavian signals (Straffron, 2021). This may be viewed in art as a vibrant illusory effect, in direct correlation with these non-human form phenotypic effects (Straffron, 2021), for the procurement of its ecological resources and territorial integrity (Borgmann, 2023; Prichard, 2016).

These aesthetic outcomes between peacocks are inherent propensities that are innate ideologies driven by inheritance, the propensity to survive in accordance with certain phenotypes in their ecosystems (Seddon, 2020). Arts have taken advantage of this ornamental aesthetics which leads the evolution of these non-human forms, with special interest to highlights the preciseness of the display of the colourful structure of its plumages as bestowed naturally on these non-human forms as actors by choice, who captures the delight of the beauty of the Zahavian signals in accordance with its expository hypothesis in the light of evolution (Phillips, 2015, Seddon, 2020).

Accessibility of Birds: In studio exploration, access to birds for creating art is done by intentionally studying them in their usual environment, though, from season to season, they migrate. During this period comprehensive study is usually done by generating essential details through observation, drawings, photographs, video recording, through digital resource and the study of works of ornithologists/illustrators. Johnson (2009) emphasises the importance of drawing directly from nature.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study used an exploratory research method with practice-led enquiry to present studio practice methods, materials, techniques, and procedures. The positive and negative results of the utilisation and practical application of materials being used to create the expository sketch step by step were explored and re-explored to properly capture the real facts both in the sketches and in the actual artwork. These were done through guided experimentation and exploratory inquiries, by technically applying brushes to paints, the introduction of canvases and other essential tools and materials to obtain the most appropriate colours and structures as represented in the natural patterns.

For perfect representation, the author used both the manual method of colour appropriation and the digital method of appropriation. These procedures and the observed outcomes were recorded to support possible re-enactment and the systemic transfer of skills.

Figure 3a: (The background ensures consistency with airy apparition gauze of illusion stage effect).
(Sketch of the Structure from figure 1a,1b, and 2a,2b above).

Figure 4:Tejuoso Patience Enifome, Revelation, Acrylic on canvas 30cm x 40cm,2025.
(Revelation(b): evocative ethereal of feminine emotion in muted tones.)

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The Lay Perspective: The audience will mainly see two human heads. The one on the left-hand side is infused horizontally on the other face on the right-hand side, without a lower jaw, eliminating the lower details of the face. Around it, lines run round it, giving an oval illusion. The feathers running through the background. While the title of the work, 'revelation', shows one of the images in a near whispering position, with the mouth lost in the dominance of the front bold facial image.

The author's Perspective: The background expresses vivid uncertainties beyond what senses and emotions can phantom, and does not consider divine intuition, spiritual bliss, or celestial rites. The conspicuous double heads depict the incompleteness of self-identity that proclaims perfection by self-induced sensitivity, self-sensation, self-doubts, self-belief, self-honor, self-adoration, and compromised self-motivation. These self-virtuosities ensure the consistent brightness in the facts of the dual head feminist being as she seeks power in disgust for peaceful co-existence, enduring survival, and equality.

The test for these ascribed liberation deepens the thoughts across board that express the fact that the self is misconstrued for the exile of feminine potency, that avenue that recreates a deconstructed humanity through divine teleportation. A Zahavian signal with short-term indirect benefits assumed by oral tradition to benefit the soul but dampens the spirit to wear off the body, in anticipation of another body, for leisure that is outside existence. A practice with excessive play, which calls for spiritual death, holding up to emotional intuition to drive psychological insights to beg for physical co-existence. Thus, the pride holds the transition of outer feminine wits that drives self-procreation, self-sameness, self-agitation for social good, and is led by self-will. A curse to the divine concept of humanity, thought the purpose of enlightenment as empowered by political freedom. The link that holds men's progenitor to the celestial concert of their ancestral contract with the Almighty.

It is essential to note that these facts shared are beyond the perception of the non-human animal forms, their beauty, and the aesthetics of their plumages. It outweighs the Zahavian concept with depths from the perception of the artist to connect facts with which the non-human actors were represented, with the illusion opposed to the fate of humanity from the multiphase dimensions of femininity.

CONCLUSION

The study used non-human animals as represented contemporary art to highlight their aesthetic potentials as forms of actors in their own right, through studio painting, using birds' plumages and the intricate arrangements of colours in their feathers as insights to present a case for Feminine proclamations.

Insights obtained from the results of the studio painting assert that the perception of the non-human animal forms, expressed in this study, presents non-human animal forms as actors' beauty and the aesthetics of their plumages as a symbolic representation of the truth about feminine perceptions, as emphasized by modern institutions. It surpassed the theoretical perception of the hypothesis of the Zahavian ideology with in-depth insights from the perception of the artist to relatively contemporary ideologies speculated by feminist movements, with which the study showcased non-human actors as hidden co-actors to represent the illusory constructs of modern feminism that are opposed to the natural fate of humanity from the multiphase dimensions of femininity.

Contribution to Knowledge: Through the studio process, original painted pieces shall add to the repertoire of visual images on the subject of birds as non-human actors in art.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends that

- i. Advocacy for the study of birds in nature, for art creation, should be intensified.
- ii. Images of birds used for art creation should be acknowledged and seen as a co-actor in the creative artwork.
- iii. An artist should study and build an archive of references for studio exploration; by doing so, their artwork will be seen as original, not just copying references.

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